

Appendix 1: Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) panel recruitment

● Criteria

1: people diagnosed with any type of cancer

Eligibility criteria

1. age \geq 18 years;
2. diagnosed with any type of cancer;
3. feel able to commit to the study for at least six months;
4. currently undergoing treatment for cancer;
5. can give informed consent;
6. can access the internet.

Exclusion criteria

1. currently involved in another study.

2: survivors of any type of cancer

Eligibility criteria

1. age \geq 18 years;
2. previously diagnosed with any type of cancer;
3. feel able to commit to the study for at least six months;
4. have completed cancer treatment and in follow-up care;
5. no major surgery is scheduled during the anticipated study period;
6. can give informed consent;
7. can access the internet.

Exclusion criteria

1. currently involved in another study.

3: informal caregivers of people with cancer

Eligibility criteria

1. age \geq 18 years;
2. feel able to commit to the study for at least six months;
3. provide the majority of unpaid, informal care for a person with cancer;
4. identified as the primary carer by people with cancer;
5. can give informed consent;
6. can access the internet.

Exclusion criteria

1. irregular and frequently changing caregivers;
2. currently involved in another study.

4: loved ones of people with cancer (family, friends)

Eligibility criteria

1. age \geq 18 years;
2. feel able to commit to the study for at least six months;
3. identified as loved ones by people with cancer;
4. can give informed consent;
5. can access the internet.

Exclusion criteria

1. currently involved in another study.

● Different characteristics expected for PPI recruitment

Participants	Expectation characteristics					Expected Total ($n=20$)
	Age	Cancer types	Education level	Ethnicity	Gender	
People diagnosed with cancer	√	√	√	√	√	7±1
Survivors of cancer	√	√	√	√	√	7±1
Informal caregivers	√		√	√	√	3±1
Loved ones	√		√	√	√	3±1

● Recruitment process

